

The Impact of Parental Decision-Making in Encouraging Children to Become Motocross Athletes in Banten Province

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ABSTRACT: Motocross is a popular sport for children and teenagers, but the sport carries a fairly serious risk of injury. Some parents who are passionate about this sport think that children or teenagers who have injuries due to slips or falls while practicing or racing motocross can recover faster, even if they have to undergo surgery, this opinion or view is not entirely true. This research aims to provide a good and factual understanding of the consequences or things that are considered and logical consequences to parents who want to include their children as Motocross athletes. This research aims to minimize the potential for injury in beginner athletes by means of education, providing understanding based on the analysis of research results. The methodology of this study uses a descriptive qualitative approach with the paradigm of constructivist communication and dialectical relational theory analysis. Primary data was obtained through in-depth interviews with five families with children who participated in the sport of motocross. Secondary data were obtained through literature studies related to the risk of injury in extreme sports. The contribution of this research is to improve parenting literacy in the context of motocross, and to provide guidance for parents to prepare their children well physically and mentally, before deciding to choose a career in motocross. This research is also expected to be a reference for motocross coaches and policymakers, whether it is the government, sports organizations or community clubs in creating a safer training system for young athletes.

KEYWORDS- Aspirations of fathers, Children, Motocross, Family, Sport Development

I. INTRODUCTION

The family is considered a fundamental unit in a broader social system with members consisting of father, mother, and children, [1]. The family is the main basis for child development, where values, beliefs, and behaviors are conveyed. Family significantly influences a child's perspective and career choices and talents, especially in terms of job aspirations and personal interests. [2] states that the family functions as a fundamental socialization agent, shaping attitudes and behaviors. Parents, especially fathers, have a considerable impact on their children's future trajectory, including choices related to sports, [3].

Family dynamics significantly influence a person's behavior and decision-making process, In a society like Indonesia, fathers often direct their children towards specific jobs or interests, including competitive sports such as motocross.

The pattern of the relationship between parents and children can reflect the harmonization of good communication and that can form optimal achievements and achievements in the field that their children are engaged in, [4]. This is because emotional support and the comprehensive role of parents are always a driver for children to develop their talents and interests to the maximum. In conditions like this, parents can provide encouragement in the form of actions or aspirations. Aspiration itself is the drive to achieve success [5], [6]. In the context of this research, the aspirations that will be highlighted are the aspirations of a father towards his

child. Father's aspirations are a form of representation of a father's desire or desire for a future achievement of his child in the family sphere, parents usually have aspirations for their children, for example how much enthusiasm and desire their children have in doing their homework at school [7]. The father's desire has a noble goal, which is to create hope to provide good knowledge, skills and competencies for his children for the present and future, to realize this, the factor of the academic level of parents also plays an important role in the quality of competence for their children [8]. This is because good education is related to a more comprehensive understanding of the importance of literacy, learning and self-development.

The father's aspirations should be in line with the strong talent potential of his child so that his son's hopes and dreams, one of which is in the field of motocross sports. Motocross is one of the favorite competitive sports for young people in their teens, and this sport is a choice as a place to channel adrenaline and show a sense of self-actualization for children to receive appreciation and appreciation from their families and communities as well as their schoolmates [9], [10]. Motocross Championship means an agility race riding a competition sports motorcycle in a circuit with a dirt track full of obstacles that are participated by 10 or more participants in 1 session [11], [12], Motocross is a sport whose type requires high agility and endurance with speed and dexterity that exceeds other sports, and also has a higher risk of injury. Motocross is an extreme sport that requires high preparation and talent, strong financial support, and consistent training. The sport often causes injuries, such as fractures and dislocations, especially if the rider is caught off guard or is not skilled in overcoming obstacles, especially if not accompanied by a professional trainer and fitness trainer [13], [14], [15].fdfd

In this context, the father's aspirations can be in the form of a father's hope for a child to become a successful professional motocross athlete and often win various championships can be achieved, avoiding non-technical things such as inconsistencies and lack of funding as well as other factors that can be obstacles [16]. The father's encouragement for his son to become a professional motocross athlete can be a guarantee for the future of his child's career and can bring a positive influence on the name of the region, bring the fragrant name of his community and also support the welfare of his life [17]. Children will be the main attention given to the family, especially fathers in choosing fields or skills that are carried out in the present and also designed for the future [18]. This explanation can be briefly called sports development or an effort to improve the role of children in sports, such as motocross, to develop their skills, discipline, and potential achievements in the present or future [17],

However, it is not uncommon for these aspirations to cause excessive pressure on children, resulting in disappointment or rejection of the expectations set [16]. Although the father's aspirations have a noble goal in providing the best for the child, it can be that if it has not been communicated well and has not provided a clear understanding, it can cause quite serious pressure for the child, this can ultimately interfere with emotional and psychological development [19]. In the context of this study, although the pattern of family communication between parents and children can create harmonious communication, there can still be conflicts or conflicts that can hinder children's optimal achievement in this motocross sport [20].

II. METHOD

This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach with a constructivist communication paradigm. The constructivism paradigm is a great choice for research on the family communication of motocross athletes and their impact on achievement and prestige. This paradigm focuses on how social reality is constructed through the interactions and meanings that individuals share within a community [21], [22], [23]. This study involved 5 informants consisting of the father of the Motocross family Champion of the National Runner Up Grade C, the father of the Motocross family of the Junior National Champion, the father of the Motocross family of the General Champion of Banten Province FFA, the Public Relations of IMI of the Banten Provincial Administrator, the father of the Motocross family of the Banten Local Class Champion. These five informants were selected on the basis of criteria that the informant has a clear connection to the research objectives and research questions based on how their contributions can inform the answers to the research questions. In addition, the five informants play the role of fathers who choose motocross as a sport for their children and have managed to win various championships at the provincial and national levels. This study uses observation and

interview techniques as a method of data collection. This study uses the theory of relational dialectics as an analysis knife.

III. RESULT

This research was conducted through in-depth interviews with several resource persons who are considered to have the capacity and observation to provide an overview of the significant implications of parents' decisions on children's development as motocross athletes. Based on the results of the study, there are significant implications of fathers' aspirations on the child's motivation to become a motocross athlete. For details, the results of the study can be seen in Table 1.

Children Name	Age	Result	Talent/Skill	Remarks
Andri Firman	17 years old	Winner Runner Up Grade C Grade National Champ	A (Highest)	Join in Motocross
Jeffry Bule	13 years old	125cc National Junior Winner	A (Highest)	Join in Motocross
Regiansyah	12 years old	Banten Province Winner	C (Medium)	Switch to Low-Risk Sport
Davi	10 years old	FFA Local District Winner	D (Poor)	Join in Touring Motorbike
Reza	9 years old	Banten Province Winner	C (Medium)	Switch to Low-Risk Sport

Table 1. Children Questionnaire Result Research

In detail, from table 1, it can be seen that Andri shows very high ability and achievement in motocross. As a runner-up and national champion in grade C, Andri has proven that his father's aspirations to push him in the motocross world have paid off. Andri also chose to stay on the motocross path, which shows the alignment between his father's aspirations and Andri's personal interests. Then Jeffry, who won the junior national championship, also showed that when there is a match between the aspirations of the father and the talents of the child, significant results can be achieved. Jeffry has the highest skills and clearly shows that the support and encouragement of his father played a big role in the achievement he was able to accomplish diraihnya.

Next is Regiansyah who managed to become the provincial winner, but his skills are considered moderate. Despite the achievements, he chose to switch to lower-risk sports. This decision reflects the incompatibility between the father's aspirations that he wanted him to continue competing in motocross and the fact that Regiansyah may feel uncomfortable with the risks that exist in the sport. The fourth subject is Davi, who has below-average skills in motocross, preferring to jump into the sport of touring motorbike, which is considered to be lower risk. Although Davi's father wanted him to excel in motocross, Davi preferred a safer path, which showed a tension between parental aspirations and the child's interests or prowess. Finally, just like Regiansyah, Reza also chose to switch to lower-risk sports even though he had achieved in motocross. Reza's choice indicated that although he could win provincial competitions, he felt that lower-risk sports were more in line with his interests and preferences.

Although Davi's father wanted him to excel in motocross, Davi preferred a safer path, which showed a tension between parental aspirations and the child's interests or prowess. Finally, just like Regiansyah, Reza also chose to switch to lower-risk sports even though he had achieved in motocross. Reza's choice indicated that although he could win provincial competitions, he felt that lower-risk sports were more in line with his interests and preferences. The results of this observation then become the basis for the father's aspirational decision, if the

child seems to have seriousness and the results of the initial race get results that are proud of the first to third place, then the father then includes his son to pursue this motocross sport more intensively, but if the results of his father's observation of his son show less than optimal results and also the seriousness and seriousness are lacking, Then the father will find another sport that is more suitable and preferred by his child. Based on the results of observations and interviews, in this case there is no conflict in the selection of sports interests and talents from the child, so that no internal conflicts were found between the research subjects.

The first paragraph under each heading or subheading should be flush left, and subsequent paragraphs should have a five-space indentation. A colon is inserted before an equation is presented, but there is no punctuation following the equation. All equations are numbered and referred to in the text solely by a number enclosed in a round bracket (i.e., (3) reads as "equation 3"). Ensure that any miscellaneous numbering system you use in your paper cannot be confused with a reference [4] or an equation (3) designation.

IV. DISCUSSION

Fathers have a great influence on their children's achievements. A good father-child relationship also affects the emotional development and well-being of children. When fathers spend more time with their children, especially during infancy and toddlerhood, children tend to have higher emotional security, self-esteem, and confidence. A study based on a representative sample of nearly 5,000 mother-and-father households in the UK, showed paternal involvement had a positive impact on children's achievement regardless of gender, ethnicity, age, school year, or household income. In line with this, in the context of this study, namely in the motocross environment, the involvement and aspirations of the father are very influential, however, the results still depend on the interests and talents of the child. When the child's interests and talents match the father's aspirations, the achievements achieved will be higher as shown by Andri and Jeffry, however, when parents' expectations and children's desires do not match, as Regiansyah, Davi, and Reza show, children tend to choose to switch to other sports, other than motocross.

Related to the theory used in this study, it is proven that the theory of Relational Dialectics is able to well elaborate the phenomenon that occurs in the decision-making process of children to their father's request to become a professional motocross racer. In the context of Dialectical Relational theory, It is important to understand that tension in family communication is not always negative,

(Navarro-Haro et al., 2024). Such tension can be a source of innovation and growth in relationships. For example, conflicts between family members can spark deep discussions and creative problem-solving, which ultimately strengthens family bonds and deepens understanding of each other. These tensions often reflect the dynamics that are natural in an ever-evolving relationship and can serve as a catalyst for positive change and increased family adaptation to new situations. In this context, there are two possibilities that arise. Some children agreed to the request and managed to achieve achievements, even becoming national champions. However, there are also children who choose to disagree with their father's aspirations.

However, in this situation, the father does not impose his will on the child, but rather gives full support for his child to choose another sports path that better suits their talents and interests. This father's approach reflects an attitude that prioritizes children's freedom in making choices, without neglecting the important role of parental support in helping children develop their potential.

Parental involvement has been shown to improve children's performance and participation in various domains, including sports [25]. There is a strong connection between parental support and children's involvement in sport, self-esteem, and performance evaluation, [26]. A variety of factors, including fun, influence a child's decision to participate in sports [27]. Importantly, extrinsic and intrinsic factors influence a child's enjoyment of a particular sport, with parental participation being the main extrinsic variable. Moreover Krijan dkk. [28], emphasizes that a child's enjoyment of a particular sport is significantly influenced by the right parental support.

Additionally, a child's perception of their parents' involvement can affect their likelihood of participating in sports. Conversely, inadequate parental involvement can adversely affect the enjoyment of exercising. Research shows that adolescent athletes often experience stress due to parental expectations, which may result from their understanding of parental interest in their accomplishments [29].

Parental pressure can adversely affect sports performance, resulting in anxiety, dissatisfaction, and risk avoidance. Dunn, Dorsch, King, dan Rothlisberger [30], proposes that parental expectations can be a considerable source of stress for young athletes. This pressure can arise from athletes' recognition of their parents' level of dedication.

Bad influences can indeed hinder athletes' concentration and performance. Parental behavior and pressure can affect a child's athletic experience, potentially leading to decreased performance outcomes [15]. An athlete who is exposed to excessive parental "training" can experience increased stress, resulting in performance anxiety, fatigue, and reduced motivation. In conclusion, bad parental influence can lead to reduced motivation, concentration, and athletic performance.

This study has findings of results that are useful for parents, especially for fathers in the form of a deep understanding before deciding their children to pursue becoming motocross athletes, of course by considering various factors and consequences in addition to the champion target which is indeed a dream for families who want sympathy, prestige, prestige and appreciation from the community and external parties by including their children in the training of motocross athletes provinces and nationalities in Indonesia. The first finding is that of the five families of sportsmen interviewed, there are three families whose children really have high talent and in accordance with their natural talent to pursue motocross as their choice of sport, and in this case the family with full support included their children to become professional motocross athletes, from the results of the process after five years, their children have shown proud achievements, Furthermore, for the other three families, the child does not fully have talent or superior talent in the field of motocross. The above communication phenomenon occurs in a dialogue between the father and the child who clearly conveys the intention that the father's desire does not match the talent of his child, in the pattern of communication relationships between children and family members, to elaborate this interpersonal communication, as visualized through the diagram below :

Figure 1. Motocross Family Communication Relationship Pattern

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Furthermore, for the other three families, the child does not fully have talent or superior talent in the

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1. The Child's Response describes the child's response to his father's wishes. Children in their youth are in a condition of immature thinking level and tend to agree to their father's wishes without thinking about the risks of extreme motocross sports whose impact can be detrimental to the safety of the child both now and for his future in his career.
2. A Mother's response is a mother's response to the child's decision, the mother may support the child's decision or may reject it for certain reasons such as concerns for safety and security and the child's avoidance of the risk of injury.
3. Family Opinion Consolidation, This line describes the phase of responses from children, mothers, and siblings that are elaborated and deliberated together to reach a unanimous agreement or understanding in the family. At this stage, there is a process of interpersonal communication dialogue, in which the opinions of family members are supportive and some may disagree, in accordance with the theory of Relational Dialectics, which is a theory that analyzes the phenomenon of Attraction attracting the interests of several opposing things.

The analysis showed that the child did not have an adequate knowledge filter to assess the dangers associated with his father's aspirations to become a motocross athlete. This shows that the child does not have the capacity to thoroughly evaluate the long-term consequences of their decisions, whether physically, psychologically, or socially.

Previous research, such as that conducted by [31]dkk. (2024), The analysis showed that the child did not have an adequate knowledge filter to assess the dangers associated with his father's aspirations to become a motocross athlete. This shows that the child does not have the capacity to thoroughly evaluation.

Previous research shows that fathers' aspirations, as family leaders, greatly impact their ability to influence their children's decision to pursue a career in motocross. Consider the long-term consequences of their decisions, whether physically, psychologically, or socially.

This study shows that the aspirations of fathers, as family leaders, significantly influence children to pursue a career in the motocross world.

The father, who sees the potential in the sport, can see it as a path to success and recognition for his son. Pomerantz dan Wang [32] indicates that parents who have high expectations of their children often force them to pursue paths that align with their aspirations, often ignoring the child's mental and emotional readiness to deal with the associated problems. It is important to realize that, in an environment like this, young people do not have enough experience or information to judge whether an extreme sport such as motocross suits their abilities and interests. The choice to pursue a career as a motocross athlete carries considerable physical risks and requires a comprehensive understanding of potential injury, long-term health consequences, and the emotional and social challenges that may arise, as examined in the study [33] regarding the interaction between risk and decision-making in extreme sports.

It is important for parents to give their children the opportunity to explore a variety of options without undue pressure, so that they can gain a deeper understanding of themselves, their abilities and their potential, as articulated in Vygotsky's theory of social and cognitive development,(Shi, 2025).

Parental support in providing balanced information and allowing children to make assessments independently can enhance the development of mature and effective decision-making skills.

V. CONCLUSION

The data shows that fathers continue to give their children the freedom to choose the sport that works best for them, while considering and monitoring their progress in novice motocross contests. This indicates that the father's aspiration for his son to become a professional motocross champion still depends on the child's choice to approve or disapprove. The father's careful wisdom and consideration in making decisions significantly influenced the drive for the son to get involved in the sport of motocross as an athlete. This

requires evaluating the various factors and possible impacts, in addition to the aspiration to win the championship, which is often an important aspiration in the family, especially for fathers who seek empathy, status, and recognition from the community and outsiders by including their children in provincial or national motocross competitions in Indonesia.

The research contributes by offering an educational platform in the form of a beginner's kit, which acts as an initial guide for families aspiring to support their children's professional motocross careers. This increases parents' understanding and literacy regarding the sport of motocross, especially for those who have interests and aspirations in this field. This study seeks to add to the collection of papers in the field of motocross, particularly regarding inclusive communication between children and parents, a research subject that is still relatively understudied.

This study was constrained by the limited number of respondents interviewed, which hindered the generalization of the findings. This research does not currently have diverse perspectives and experiences from families with different backgrounds, which could lead to more comprehensive insights into the obstacles and support networks for aspiring motocross athletes. Additional research including larger sample sizes and a broader spectrum of family history is essential to gain a more thorough and complete understanding of this subject.

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